

РОЗДІЛ 6
ОСВІТНЄ ЛІДЕРСТВО ПІД ЧАС КРИЗИ:
ВИКЛИКИ, СТРАТЕГІЇ, ЦІННОСТІ

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**FUTURE MANAGERS' OF EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS PROFESSIONAL
TRAINING TO THE MAINTAINING EFFECTIVE EXPENDITURE MANAGEMENT**

Key words: educational institution management, manager of educational organization, education financing, budget financing, expenditure management.

Today, our country is undergoing a radical reform of the education system. The new school of the 21st century should provide education for life, develop children's individual abilities and shape personality. Under such conditions, the determinant is a competency-based approach in building a new content of education and training of Ukrainian schoolchildren. In this regard, the problem of training modern education managers to manage a general secondary education institution in conditions of market competition is becoming more and more urgent. The urgency of considering the issue of increasing the professional competence of education managers is explained by the need to resolve the contradiction that has arisen between modern requirements for the professional activity of an education manager as a holistic personality, a subject of the educational process capable of self-development, construction and implementation of humanistic pedagogical systems and technologies, and the real level of his professional competence in solving educational tasks and making management decisions. It is education managers who should become the driving force for the revival and creation of a qualitatively new national education [Sayuk].

It should be noted that it is quite important to determine the importance of increasing the managerial and financial education of heads of educational organizations under conditions of decentralization and the ability to effectively distribute expenses. Given the political and socio-economic changes in Ukraine, efforts aimed at increasing financial literacy and developing the psychological and pedagogical competence of future managers in the educational sphere are appropriate and urgent.

The need to increase the amount of budget funds invested in the development of education is caused by the tasks of increasing the efficiency and competitiveness of the economy, structural changes in the employment sector, which determine the constant need for improving the qualifications and training of personnel, and increasing their professional mobility. It is financial investments in education that are recognized as one of the most important investments in human capital [Voloshyn].

The main tasks of a manager at any level and in any educational organization are: determining the goal of management, stimulating activities, communication at all levels, as well as continuous control and reporting.

Developing an effective cost management system is an important task for managers of educational institutions. Accordingly, the creation of an effective cost management system involves systematic monitoring of actual expenses and their behavior under the influence of

both internal and external factors, making decisions on improving the structure of expenses and their management [Voloshyn].

The effective distribution and size of expenses is the main factor for assessing the effectiveness of the institution's activities, and also significantly affects the formation of the financial result of the educational institution.

The development of national education systems is determined by socio-economic factors and political conditions specific to each country, which have their own trajectory and life cycle of existence. It is quite popular to believe that higher education expenditures are investments with a long-term economic effect [Kovernik]. The sphere of education for successful functioning requires provision of sufficient financial resources. Education finance is a system of monetary relations regarding the formation, distribution and use of various financial resources or funds of funds. As a result of the implementation of these relations in educational activities, various funds of financial resources are formed, the purpose of which is to ensure the effective functioning of educational institutions [Kyrychenko].

Of course, budgetary institutions and organizations have their own revenues (special fund), received in the established manner as a fee for the provision of services, performance of works, etc., in accordance with their functional powers.

The funds of the special fund are used to carry out activities related to the performance of basic functions that are not provided (or partially provided) by the expenditures of the general fund. However, today's realities emphasize that in order for state institutions and organizations to achieve a significant economic effect in terms of using general and special funds, the issue of expenditure management is particularly important. It is their volume and composition that affect the functioning of such enterprises, which in turn must ensure the level of development and education of the state.

Management involves the performance of such functions as planning, organization, coordination, motivation, control and others, which provides conditions for productive and effective work of employees employed in the organization and obtaining results that would correspond to the set goals. Along with this, it is worth emphasizing that the orientation of the managerial activity of the head of a general secondary education institution is pedagogical in its essence, because even when the head solves economic or financial tasks, he does so in order to achieve the ultimate pedagogical goal.

To ensure effective management, it is necessary to organize the management of expenses in various aspects, in particular: by technologies (conventional, intensive, etc.), centers of responsibility, types of products, by responsible persons, which allows comprehensively analyzing the level of expenses and determining their compliance with established norms and on this basis developing one's own expense management policy, applying effective methods and mechanisms at all levels of management. In modern conditions, the process of expense management is conditioned by the economic and financial independence of organizations. Economic independence consists in the ability to choose organizational activities, and accordingly, the responsibility of managers for the decisions made increases significantly. The effectiveness of the functioning of an educational institution largely depends on the rational use of all types of resources, which necessitates the need for a gradual transition to a unified expense management system.

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PROFESSIONAL BURNOUT AMONG DOCTORS, NURSES AND PARAMEDICS

Abstract

The purpose of the presented master's thesis was to analyze the differences in levels of burnout in doctors, nurses and paramedics. The study was based on Christina Maslach's theory of occupational burnout. The Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) questionnaire was used, which measures three dimensions of burnout: depersonalization, personal accomplishment and emotional exhaustion.

A total of 181 participants, 71 men and 110 women, working in hospitals, clinics, emergency stations and other health care facilities were examined.

The results showed that doctors, nurses and paramedics did not differ in terms of emotional exhaustion. On the other hand, statistically significant differences were found between doctors, nurses and paramedics in the levels of the other variables: depersonalization and reduced sense for personal accomplishment.

The presented study contributes to the existing knowledge on professional burnout in groups at particular risk of developing it, namely doctors, nurses and paramedics.

Keywords: burnout, doctors, nurses, paramedics

Wprowadzenie

Wypalenie zawodowe dotyka pracowników, którym stawia się wysokie wymagania, m.in. w zakresie umiejętności uważnego słuchania i komunikacji, zdolności do empatii, okazywania zainteresowania, wspierania i świadczenia pomocy w rozwiązywaniu problemów innych ludzi. Do grupy szczególnego ryzyka należą lekarze, pielęgniarki oraz ratownicy medyczni, o których traktuje to wystąpienie.